

Self cooling functionality via vascular channel heat transit in an epoxy matrix

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1 SUMMARY

Vascular networks within polymer matrix composites have been developed in recent years. The systems offer a wide range of functionality including self-healing, self-sensing and also thermal control. This paper has looked at utilising internal vascular architecture within an epoxy matrix to control the part temperature via circulation of fluids. Networks have been created through the embedding and removal of sacrificial fibres. Parts were exposed to heat in contact/conduction and non-contact/convection experiments. Vascular components with fluid circulation exhibited as much as 73% heat reduction for conduction and 48% heat reduction for convection experiments, when compared to non-vascular parts. Components were also trialled in a freeze-thaw experiment.

2 INTRODUCTION

Smart functional materials are a viable future goal for advanced applications in aerospace, space and medical structures. Microvascular networks embedded within polymer matrix composites have been realised. Internal void architecture within a component can be utilised as service channels to deliver tailored fluids through a structure, and so offering the additional aspect of multi-functionality. Vascular channels can be achieved at scales ranging from 200µm to 500µm diameter via the embedding and subsequent thermal removal of sacrificial fibres within traditional carbon or glass fibre reinforcement. Sacrificial fibres have previously been developed via the solution treatment of Poly (lactic acid) PLA fibres in a bath of 60% Trifluoroethanol 40% H²O dispersed with 10wt% tin (II) oxalate [1]. Chemical treatment of PLA fibres reduces the thermal degradation temperature allowing fibres to be thermally removed from a cured composite post consolidation [2]. An alternative method has been developed for the up-scaled production of sacrificial fibres, utilising polymer extrusion of PLA with a powder catalyst filler. Fibres may be extruded continuously with full control over fibre diameter and catalyst fill content. Sacrificial components can be produced with reduced variability, at higher production rates and lower cost than previous methods [3].

Utilising these methods vascular components have been developed. Functionality has been achieved through self cooling/thermal control experiments. Channel architecture has been used to deliver and circulate liquid coolant throughout the internal profile of an epoxy based specimen. Self cooling experiments have displayed high potential for advanced thermal control. Successful experiments have indicated cooling systems can be highly efficient in providing heat transit through a component. Vascular components with circulating coolants have maintained temperatures over 50% lower than virgin components under identical thermal influence.

Polymer composites have traditionally been excluded from hot applications including engine components due to the low thermal capability of matrix materials. A self cooling component may broaden the application of composites, moreover a vascular component may indeed be both cooled or heated for de-icing function. Many efforts have been made to enhance the thermal properties of polymer composite material. The majority of research has been dedicated to development of flame

retardant polymers or polymer coatings. Graphite and graphene based nano materials can be used as both matrix fillers [4] and as coating products [5] with varying degrees of success. Advanced metallic fillers like aluminium hypophosphite [6] and melamine cyanurate [7] have also been successful in increasing the thermal performance/ fire retardant properties of polymer materials. As with any functional filler, the contribution towards other properties like mechanical must be considered. The mechanical integrity of a polymer composite may be tested under a thermal influence. Fire exposure can also be simulated for structural integrity under load [8]. The polymer matrix material itself must be selected based on its thermal performance, as a filler or coating will only enhance existing properties. Fire retardant additives/polymers will repel flame and withstand high temperatures, however they cannot offer cooling properties. A self-cooling composite has the ability to transport heat away from the component and regulate the localised temperature.

The main mechanisms of heat transfer throughout a vascular component must be considered. Conduction, convection and advection occur at different points in the heat cycle. It is important to consider the component under thermal influence. The sample is a solid (epoxy) with void channels running through its centre. Fluid (water) is moving through the void channels under pressure. The solid epoxy structure is the first material subjected to heat energy. Conduction is the first mechanism to begin under the laws of thermodynamics. Heat is transferred from the source (in this case a hotplate) into the solid matrix sample. These items are in thermal contact and will obey a thermal contact conductance coefficient and Fouriers law.

As the solid matrix tries to reach thermal equilibrium, heat will radiate from the heated surface to the unheated surface. In the centre plane of the solid matrix the void channels carry high pressure coolant through the part. As the heat energy moves through the matrix the channels heat up also. At this point convection will occur. At first there is heat transfer through the boundary plane (vascular channel inner walls). Heat energy is transferred from the solid matrix material to the fluid coolant. Heat diffusion initially occurs within the fluid itself however as the fluid is also flowing through the void channel this is quickly followed by advection.

What must also be considered is the void architecture. Increases in internal surface area will increase the boundary plane between the heating solid and the coolant liquid. Increases in surface area will result in higher heat transfer efficiency. However for structural components void architecture may have limitations due to negative mechanical contribution. Another consideration for increased surface area is the path of the channels. Linear channels have less total surface area than nonlinear or meandering channels of identical cross section due to higher total length.

Figure 1. a) SEM image of micro-channel

b) Optical microscope image of braided vascular channels

Figure 2. Layout of conduction experiments

Figure 3. Layout of convection experiments

Heat flow between solids and fluids can be calculated using the heat transfer coefficient. For this there are many considerations including the geometry of the void architecture, the properties of the boundary plane and the properties of the substances in question (solid and liquid). Also factored is the pressure and flow of the fluid, the direction of flow to gravity and heat source, the viscosity of the fluid and the internal topography of the channel walls. What must also be considered is the effect of heat transfer through multiple materials with different thermal conductivities (two materials in this case, but may be three or more if considering a composite of fibre, matrix and fluid coolant). Each material will heat and cool at different rates. Also each material will exhibit different coefficients of thermal expansion which may contribute to fluid pressure. It can be stated that the goal of a self cooling vascular system is to delay or stop thermal equilibrium being reached for a solid under heat influence. This can be achieved through the continuous transit of fluid coolants through the part under heat influence. It can be presumed that temperature should plateau depending on the experimental conditions.

3 METHODS AND MATERIALS

Vascular components were developed via methods described previously [1]. PLA monofilament of 500 μm diameter was used as received from Monofil Technik UK. The catalyst tin (II) oxalate and solvent Trifluoroethanol were used as received from Sigma-Aldrich UK. The Huntsman epoxy system; Araldite LY 564 with Aradure 2954 cure agent was used as a matrix. Following fibre treatment techniques [2], sacrificial fibre components were developed and cured into epoxy casts. Vascular epoxy samples were prepared with 30mm x 10mm cross-sectional area. Samples contained 6 linear 500 μm channels running through the central horizontal X,Y axis spaced 4mm apart. Channel feed ends were tapped with 0.6mm hypodermic needles which self sealed in the holes. Ports were joined via tubing to a manifold off which a single pressurised water input was fastened.

Samples were heated via two methods; conduction heating and convection heating. For conduction experiments samples were placed on a hot plate, in full contact with the steel heating surface and subject to thermal contact conductance. No force is added to hold the part to the hotplate. For convection experiments samples were placed within an air circulated oven. Parts were not in contact with any heating elements. Both hot plate and oven temperatures were recorded during experiments.

For freeze-thaw experiments, both vascular and non-vascular components were placed into a freezer for 48 h. Parts were sprayed with water intermittently during the 48 h period to develop a frosting. Thermocouples were adhered to both vascular and non-vascular samples prior to all experiments. Data was collected on an 8 channel Pico data logger.

4 EXPERIMENTS

Both conduction and convection experiments were performed with two methods; a cold start where fluids were circulated from the beginning of experiments when parts are cold, and a hot start where fluid circulation is started after the components have been heated, to observe the systems ability to reduce the temperature of a hot part. Fluid flow rates were kept to 165 ml/min per channel and readings were taken of fluid temperatures going in and coming out of vascular parts during experiments. The glass transition temperatures (T_g) of the epoxy system for vascular components by the manufacturer as 130-153°C depending on the cure cycle selected. Subsequently temperature ramps for cooling experiments did not exceed this temperature window, as it is beyond the service temperature for the resin, for which a self-cooling vascular network would not be applicable.

For conduction experiments the vascular and non-vascular parts were placed on the same hot plate for consistency. Whilst there was no control over heating rates, they were calculated from the graphs. For cold start experiments the fluid circulation was started prior to the heating of parts. The experiment was run until the non-vascular component reached ~140 °C, after which the temperature was removed and parts were allowed to equilibrate. For hot start conduction, both parts were heated to ~120 °C, before the coolant circulation was started. The experiment was stopped after the vascular part was returned to average service temperatures.

Figure 4. Conduction experiment showing hot plate set up

Figure 5. Convection experiment showing oven set up

For convection cold start experiments, fluid flow was again initiated from the beginning of the heat cycle. The run was stopped when the non-vascular component reached the T_g window. In hot start experiments both parts were heated until the T_g window was reached, at which point the fluid flow was initiated in the vascular part. The experiment was stopped when the vascular component reached a constant temperature. Freeze-thaw experiments were conducted using the same components as the cooling experiments. Initially room temperature water was circulated through the frozen vascular part, the fluid temperature was then ramped. The experiment was run until the vascular part was returned to a typical service temperature range.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physical experiments have been successful, however the techniques prove difficult to manage and pose some considerations for procedure. The first consideration is the efficiency of the vascular network itself. Due to the scale of the device it is difficult to develop systems that are without flaw; i.e. small leaks in the connections. This is due to the physical nature of securing micro-couplings to the vasculature, and the charging of micro-channels and related architecture with pressurised fluids. However in most cases efficiency was achieved throughout the experiment.

The most profound temperature reductions have been observed for conduction experiments. For both hot and cold starts 73% efficiency has been achieved. For the cold start conduction experiment (Fig. 7) for which the coolant is circulated from the beginning of the run, the non-vascular part reaches a maximum temperature (T_m) of 139 °C at a heating rate of 3.2 °C/min. The T_m of the vascular component under the same heat influence is 37 °C at a heating rate of 0.5 °C. The plate heats up at 7.0

Figure 6. Freeze-thaw experiment

Experiment	Fluid flow (ml/min)	Fluid temp. in (°C)	Fluid temp. out (°C)	Plate/oven heating rate (°C/min)	Plate/oven max temp. (°C)	Part heating rate (°C/min)		Part cooling rate (°C/min)		Part max temp. (°C)		Vascular part temp. reduction (°C)	Functionality efficiency (%) V - Vascular NV-Non-vascular
						vasc	Non-vasc	vasc	Non-vasc	vasc	Non-vasc		
Conduction cold start	165			7.0	265	0.5	3.2	0.5	3.5	37	139	102	73 ($\frac{T_{max}^{NV} - T_{max}^V}{T_{max}^V}$)
Conduction hot start	165	15	22	8.6	279	3.2	3.2	9.7	1.1	114	136	77	73 ($\frac{T_{max}^{NV} - T_{min}^V}{T_{max}^V}$)
Convection cold start	165	17	32	1.7	174	0.8	1.5			157	91	66	42 ($\frac{T_{max}^{NV} - T_{max}^V}{T_{max}^V}$)
Convection hot start	165	17	60	2.7	174	2.2	2.2	2.7		147	153	68	48 ($\frac{T_{max}^{NV} - T_{min}^V}{T_{min}^V}$)

Table 1. Experimental data from conduction and convection experiments

Experiment	Fluid flow (ml/min)	Fluid temp. in (°C)	Fluid temp. out (°C)	Chiller temp. (°C)	Part heating rate (°C/min) (Vasc.)	Part min temp. (°C)		Part max temp. (°C)		Vascular part temp. increase (°C)	Functionality efficiency (%)
						vasc	Non-vasc	vasc	Non-vasc		
Freeze-thaw	165	48	17	-29	2.2	-19	-33	35	-33	54	284 ($T_{\min} V - T_{\max} V$)

Table 2. Experimental data from freeze-thaw experiments

°C/min to a maximum of 265 °C. The heat influence is reduced at this point to observe the time taken for both parts to return to room temperature which is ~16.5 and ~33 minutes for vascular and non-vascular respectively; taking approximately twice as long for non-vascular parts to cool. For hot start conduction experiments (Fig. 8), both parts are heated at the same rate (3.2 °C) before the coolant is introduced to the vascular part. The experiment is conducted to observe the ability of the system to return a heated part to temperatures closer to ambient. The coolant is turned on approaching the ~120 °C mark, after which the vascular part returns to 37 °C within 8 minutes at a rate of 9.7 °C/min. The heater T_m at the point of coolant charge is 279 °C. The vascular component again returns 73% temperature reductions (in comparison to the non-vascular T_m of 136 °C).

In cold start convection experiments (Fig. 9), the oven heated at 1.7 °C/min to a T_m of 174 °C. Non-vascular parts heat in this environment at 1.5 °C/min to a T_m of 157 °C after ~95 minutes. Within the same time frame and environment the vascular part (with coolant on) heats at a rate of 0.8 °C/min to a T_m of 91 °C. At the 95 minute mark the oven, non-vascular and vascular temperatures begin to plateau. At this point the vascular component can be observed to exhibit stable temperature reductions of 42%. In hot start convection experiments (Fig. 10), both parts are heated at 2.2 °C/min. The coolant is activated at ~140 °C after which the vascular part cools at 2.7 °C/min, to reach 79 °C after 25 minutes. This is a 48% temperature reduction on the non-vascular T_m .

The freeze-thaw experiments show similar efficiencies (Fig. 11), (Table 2). The vascular part is maintained at -19 °C. Heavy frosting is observed on all surfaces of the part at this temperature (Fig. 6). The fluid is initially charged at ambient temperatures to avoid the potential of cracking the epoxy from thermal shock. Ambient temperature fluid circulation is observed to elevate the part temperature from -19 °C to freezing point after ~6 minutes. During this event the temperature of the fluid is raised significantly to ~50 °C, inducing a rapid rise in part temperature from freezing point to 30 °C at 3.5 °C/min.

Figure 7. Cold start conduction experiments (hot plate)

A high degree of efficiency has been achieved across all experimental approaches. For conduction experiments, heat reduction has had the highest degree of success for both hot and cold starts. This may be due to two factors. Although hot plates reach much higher temperatures than oven temperatures, much of the energy from the hot plate escapes into the atmosphere. In the oven the heat energy is for the most part contained. Also the convection heated parts are heated from all surfaces as opposed to in conduction experiments where parts are heated only from one side. Another consideration is that in the oven experiments, the pipe work to deliver coolant into the parts had to also run through the oven. Subsequently this pipe work also heated up with the parts. Warm pipes resulted in the temperatures of the coolant rising before reaching the part, and so the heat transfer is affected.

Figure 8. Hot start conduction experiment (hot plate)

Figure 9. Cold start convection experiment (oven)

This is not observed in the fluid temperatures (Table 1), because the thermocouples were placed in the pipe work outside the oven. If the thermocouples were placed in the pipe work inside the oven they would also be affected by the oven temperatures. Unfortunately in both cases, results will be affected.

For freeze-thaw experiments, the predominant issue is the freezing of fluids in the channels. If there are residual fluids in the channels these will also freeze, blocking the channel and rendering it temporarily obsolete. When blocked channels are charged with fluids they do eventually clear, however this is not an ideal scenario. This could be addressed by possibly charging the channels with high pressure or high temperature air to remove residual moisture. The systems have proven also to be versatile. The same components and system architecture has been used for both cooling and freeze-thaw experiments. This would point to the ability for the system to be used in robust applications such as in aircraft, where the same parts may need to be cooled in one environment and de-iced in a later environment.

Figure 10. Hot start convection experiment (oven)

Figure 11. Freeze-thaw experiment

6. CONCLUSION

Self-cooling materials with internal vascular architecture have been developed and trialled via temperature control experiments. The systems have proven to be efficient, robust and reliable in maintaining the functionality of temperature control under external thermal influences. Heat transfer into a solid material may happen either via contact/conduction and/or environment/convection. In both scenarios the vascular components exhibit excellent capabilities for reducing and maintaining temperatures within the service temperature of the epoxy matrix material. Moreover the components also offer excellent de-icing performance within a freeze-thaw experiment. The implications of a polymer or polymer composite with thermal control capabilities are profound. The loss of mechanical performance for polymers under temperature extremes often excludes them from certain advanced design applications. Vascular network incorporation may be proposed as an ideal solution for the up-performance of current advanced composite materials.

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